

Title

From sputtered metal precursors towards $\text{Cu}_2\text{Zn}(\text{Sn}_{1-x}\text{Ge}_x)\text{Se}_4$ thin film solar cells with shallow back grading

C. Andres *, A. Cabas-Vidani, A. N. Tiwari, Y. E. Romanyuk

Laboratory for Thin Films and Photovoltaics, Empa – Swiss Federal Laboratories for Materials Science and Technology, Ueberlandstrasse 129, 8600 Duebendorf, Switzerland

* Corresponding author: e-mail: christian.andres@empa.ch, Phone: +41 58 765 48 17, Fax: +41 58 765 40 42

Abstract

Bandgap grading is often employed in thin film solar cell absorbers for creating the back surface field that can reduce interface recombination at the back contact. Here, we investigate different pathways to obtain back graded $\text{Cu}_2\text{Zn}(\text{Sn}_{1-x}\text{Ge}_x)\text{Se}_4$ thin film solar cells based on a co-sputtered metal precursor and rapid thermal annealing route. The absorber bandgap can be precisely tuned for the whole compositional range of $x=0\dots 1$. While Ge does not accumulate towards the back in absorbers fabricated from uniform precursor, Ge-back graded absorbers can be obtained from stacked metal precursors. A linear back grading with a bandgap energy difference of up to 40 meV has been achieved. However, no significant improvement in open-circuit voltage and near-infrared response could be observed for the kesterite devices. This indicates that even steeper gradients are required to obtain an effective back surface field.

Keywords: thin films solar cells, kesterite, sputtering, grading.

1. Introduction

The highest efficiency of Kesterite ($\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSn}(\text{S},\text{Se})_4$ or CZTS) thin film solar cells is currently limited to 12.6%[1], which is often explained by a high open-circuit voltage deficit ($V_{\text{OC,def}}$). The origin of the $V_{\text{OC,def}}$ can be generally attributed into bulk recombination and interface recombination[2]. In kesterite thin film devices, recombination can take place either at the back interface Mo/CZTS or at the front interface of the absorber with the buffer layer. In this work we focus on the back interface and investigate if a reduction in the back interface recombination can lead to a reduction of the $V_{\text{OC,def}}$. In chalcogenide thin film solar cells, the molybdenum back contact usually reacts with the chalcogen to form $\text{Mo}(\text{S},\text{Se})_2$. For the case of kesterite, a decomposition reaction of the kesterite phase can occur at the same time[3], which can lead to additional recombination at the back interface. Recently, it has been shown for low bandgap $\text{Cu}(\text{In},\text{Ga})\text{Se}_2$ (CIGS, $E_g=1.00$ eV), which previously suffered from a significant $V_{\text{OC,def}}$ that a gallium back grading can improve the V_{OC} by over 100 mV[4] by introducing the so-called back surface field (BSF) at the back interface. We investigate if a similar back grading can be achieved by using germanium in $\text{Cu}_2\text{Zn}(\text{Sn}_{1-x}\text{Ge}_x)\text{Se}_4$ solar cells.

From first principle calculations for $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnGeSe}_4$ a bandgap of 1.5 eV was calculated when replacing Sn with Ge[5], which is close to the experimentally found value of 1.52 eV[6]. For the solid solution with sulfur ($\text{Cu}_2\text{Zn}(\text{Sn}_{1-x}\text{Ge}_x)(\text{S},\text{Se})_4$) the bandgap can be increased even further[7]. For pure selenide ($\text{Cu}_2\text{Zn}(\text{Sn}_{1-x}\text{Ge}_x)\text{Se}_4$) compounds, it was shown that the bandgap increases linear for $x=0-1$ [8]. Therefore, germanium can be used for bandgap grading in kesterite solar cells in analogy to gallium in CIGSe. Bandgap grading has been reported so far only for the sulfo-selenide $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSn}(\text{S},\text{Se})_4$ compounds[9–12] or a Ag containing alloy [13]. For a sputtered stacked precursor arrangement with Ge as the top layer, it was shown that Ge can preferentially diffuse towards the back[14]. However, no $\text{Cu}_2\text{Zn}(\text{Sn}_{1-x}\text{Ge}_x)\text{Se}_4$ devices with Ge back grading have been reported so far.

In this work, we address the following scientific questions: (1) Is there a preferential diffusion of Ge in a fully mixed precursor? (2) Can a pronounced Ge back grading be realized from sputtered metal precursor? (3) Does a Ge back grading improve the $V_{\text{OC,def}}$ of kesterite solar cells?

In order to address the first question, a series of uniformly mixed metal precursors with Ge/(Ge+Sn) (GGT) = 0...1 are fabricated and their bandgaps are measured for a given GGT.

With this knowledge, a series of different precursor arrangements is produced in order to obtain a Ge back grading in the final absorber (Figure 1). The arrangements consist of:

- *Uniform precursor*: has a fixed GGT ratio within the whole depth.
- *Graded precursor*: consists of a 400 nm plateau with a low GGT which increases to a high GGT value towards the back within a depth of 100 nm.
- *Stacked precursor*: 400 nm low GGT layer is stacked on top of a 100 nm high GGT layer.

Having in mind Fick's second law for one dimension (which can sufficiently describe the diffusion of Ge from the back to the front):

$$\frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial t} = D \frac{\partial^2 \varphi}{\partial x^2}$$

where φ is the concentration of Ge depending on time t and position x and D the diffusion constant which increases with temperature, additional two arrangements for the stacked precursor are tested in order to achieve a stronger gradient: The stacked precursor is annealed at reduced time (5 min -> 2 min) and reduced temperature (550°C -> 500°C) (named "fast"). The thickness of the top layer is doubled in order to increase the total diffusion length (named "thick").

2. Experimental details

The Mo back contact was deposited using DC sputtering on top of soda lime glass with SiO_x as the alkali diffusion barrier. A mixed metal precursor was deposited by co-sputtering of elemental metal targets at room temperature in a con-focal arrangement (AJA ATC-Orion 5 system from AJA Inc.). The integrated precursor composition with Cu/(II+IV) ~ 0.75 and Zn/IV ~ 1.15 was measured by X-ray fluorescence. Prior to the annealing, a 1.15 μm thick Se capping layer was thermally evaporated on top[15]. In a rapid thermal annealing (RTA) system (AS-ONE from Annealsys), the precursor was heated

to 550°C for 5 minutes with additional Se pellets (800 mg) in a closed graphite reactor. The annealing was performed using a nitrogen base pressure of 62500 Pa and fast heating and cooling rates (from room temperature to 550°C at a rate of 4°C/s and cooling from 550°C to 300°C in 5 min).

CZTSe absorbers were subsequently covered with a CdS buffer by chemical bath deposition without further surface treatment, followed by the deposition of the i-ZnO/ZnO:Al window by RF magnetron sputtering. In the final step a Ni/Al grid was applied by e-beam evaporation and individual cells (0.36 cm²) were mechanically scribed. No anti-reflection coating was applied. The bulk composition was determined by using X-ray fluorescence (XRF, 45 kV acceleration voltage). X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns were obtained in the Bragg–Brentano geometry on a X'Pert PRO diffractometer (Cu-K_{α1} radiation, $\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$) from 10 to 80° (2 θ) with a step interval of 0.0167°. Depth profiling data were obtained with a time-of-flight Secondary Ion Mass Spectroscopy (SIMS) 5 system from ION-TOF. Bi⁺ ions were used as primary ions and positive ions were detected. Sputtering was performed using O₂⁺ sputtering ions with 2 keV ion energy, 400 nA ion current and a 300×300 μm² raster size. An area of 100×100 μm² was analyzed using Bi⁺ ions with 25 keV ion energy and 3.1 pA ion current. The CZTSe solar cell devices were characterized by current-density–voltage (JV) and external quantum efficiency (EQE) measurements under standard test conditions (AM 1.5G spectrum, 25 °C, 1000 W/m²). The bandgap of the corresponding solar cells was obtained from the inflection point of the EQE.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Bandgap tuning for Cu₂Zn(Sn_{1-x}Ge_x)Se₄ for x=0-1

A series of samples with different Ge content was fabricated by co-sputtering of Cu, Zn, Sn and Ge metal targets and their compositions were measured by XRF (Table 1). It can be seen that the composition of the metal precursor can be precisely controlled by the sputtering rates and is maintained after rapid thermal annealing. A slight Ge loss[16,17] occurs during the annealing, which has the same order of magnitude as for Sn, keeping the GGT ratio constant. Fig. 2 shows the (112) Bragg peak for varying Ge content. The 2 θ angle is increasing with increasing Ge content, which suggests a full incorporation into the kesterite lattice, thereby confirming results recently reported for co-evaporated kesterite absorber[8]. In contrast to the co-evaporated absorber, a broadening of the (112) peak for a GGT towards 0.50 is observed, which might correlate with the abundance of the ZnSe

peak at 27.23°. After finishing the devices, the bandgap can be derived from the inflection point in the EQE measurement (Fig. 3). When increasing GGT from 0 to 1, the extracted bandgap can be increased from 1.00 eV to 1.44 eV and can be approximated with the empirically found linear relationship:

$$E_g = 0.448 \cdot GGT + 0.9985 \text{ eV}$$

3.2. Uniform precursor

For each sample described in 3.1 SIMS measurements were performed so that the GGT ratio and the respective bandgap can be related to the absolute counts. This enables the calculation of the relative bandgap shift from a GGT depth profile. An example for a sample with a GGT of 0.17 is given in Fig. 4. In contrast to [14], where Ge diffused from the top of the stack preferentially to the back, the GGT profile of the absorber from a uniform precursor remains flat across the absorber thickness. The same observation is made for other samples in the whole GGT range. It should be noted, that the Na content and profile remain unaffected by the Ge content and they exhibit similar characteristics as the undoped reference in [18], which is in contrast to the observations made for a stacked metal precursor in [19]. This might be due to the use of the alkali diffusion barrier and the overall lower Na quantity in our samples.

3.3. Graded precursor

Since no preferential diffusion of Ge towards the back is observed for uniform samples, an intentional Ge grading has to be induced. The concept of co-sputtering offers the flexibility to modify the sputtering rates of the metals during the deposition, thus, a metal gradient can be induced at the precursor stage. Ideally, this is done by counteracting the sputtering rates of Ge and Sn to the desired GGT ratio, while keeping Cu/(Ge+Sn) and Zn/(Ge+Sn) constant. An example of a depth profile from a weakly graded precursor (lower GGTs) is given in Fig. 5 (left). After the RTA, Ge diffused towards the front even for strongly graded precursor (Fig. 5 (right)), thereby eliminating the initially graded Ge profile. Therefore no pronounced Ge grading in the absorber could be obtained from the graded metal precursor as a consequence of complete intermixing during the selenization stage.

3.4. Stacked precursor

Another attempt to implement a back gradient in the absorber is the stacked precursor arrangement, where the element which is responsible for a higher bandgap is located at the back side. As

summarized in [20], several manufacturers for CIGS modules are using a Mo/Cu-Ga/In precursor stack which is prepared by DC-sputtering. In kesterite, a similar route could be realized by using adequate alloys as targets, e.g. Mo/Cu-Zn-Ge/Sn. In our case of co-sputtering, a stack consisting of two mixed Cu-Zn-Sn-Ge layers with different GGT is used to avoid changes in the kesterite formation pathway compared to our reference uniform precursor. In this stack, a 100 nm thick mixed Cu-Zn-Sn-Ge precursor with a GGT of 0.67 is deposited on Mo followed by a 400 nm thick film with a GGT of 0.17. The depth profile of the selenized absorber (Fig. 6 (left)) exhibits a similar flat profile as the one from the uniform precursor, suggesting a strong interdiffusion of Ge and Sn.

In order to inhibit the interdiffusion, we also performed an annealing with reduced time (from 5 min to 2min) and temperature (from 550°C to 500°C). As presented in Fig. 6 (center), the depth profile shows a plateau at the front and a slight gradient towards the back contact. The difference in bandgap energy between the front plateau and the maximum of the back grading is around 40 meV. The width of the back grading is in this case only $\frac{1}{4}$ of the absorber thickness ($\sim 1-1.5 \mu\text{m}$), whereas the back grading in the case of the single graded CIGSe [4] exceeds $\frac{1}{2}$ of the absorber thickness ($\sim 2.8-3.0 \mu\text{m}$). To this point, it is not clear how this would affect the effectiveness of the grading.

In order to achieve a similar profile, the overall thickness of the precursor stack has been increased to yield a thicker absorber layer. While keeping thickness of the high GGT layer at 100 nm, the thickness of the low GGT layer is increased to 800 nm, thereby increasing the total interdiffusion path. This precursor thickness yields a final absorber of around $2.5-3.0 \mu\text{m}$. The depth profile for this sample is given in Fig. 6 (right). The profile exhibits again a flat plateau at the front which increases steadily towards the back. The width of the grading exceeds $\frac{1}{2}$ of the absorber thickness and has a difference in bandgap energy of around 40 meV.

3.5. Opto-electronic properties

The finished cells were measured by JV and EQE and *[the photovoltaic parameters are summarized in Table 2.](#)* However, the different precursor arrangements affected the morphology of the absorber and yielded different amounts of ZnSe coverage, which has a significant impact on the fill factor and EQE maximum[15]. We focus therefore on potential differences in $V_{OC,def}$ and near-infrared collection, which are generally expected to be improved by applying a back grading. In Fig. 7 (left) a comparison of

the open-circuit voltages with respect to the Shockley-Queisser limit is given based on the following equation [21]:

$$V_{oc}/V_{oc,sq} = \frac{V_{oc}}{a \cdot E_g + b}$$

with $a = 0.928 \text{ V eV}^{-1}$ and $b = -0.176 \text{ V}$. This representation accounts for the bandgap dependent loss and ensures a better comparability between materials of different bandgaps. Comparing the absolute values, it can be seen that there is no correlation to the depth profiles, i.e. a Ge back grading does not necessarily improve the $V_{oc,def}$. In addition, from the EQE measurements (Fig. 7 (right)) no improvement in the near-infrared is observed when a Ge back grading is visible in the SIMS measurement.

4. Conclusion & Outlook

We presented different pathways to achieve a Ge back grading in kesterite thin film solar cells. First, no preferential accumulation of Ge towards the back was observed for uniform precursor. Second, a moderate back grading could be achieved with a stacked precursor. Generally, a strong interdiffusion is observed even for a short annealing time such as 5 min. The highest bandgap energy difference within the most pronounced grading was 40 meV, being significantly lower than the ones reported for single graded CIGSe[4]. Finally, no significant improvement in $V_{oc,def}$ nor in near-infrared response could be observed. Therefore, it can be assumed that a steeper Ge gradient is needed to obtain an effective BSF. In future, transmission electron microscopy measurements shall reveal if the observed gradient in SIMS is not a product of co-precipitation of kesterite grains with different Ge content. In addition, we will investigate gradings with a different steepness to clarify if back interface recombination is limiting the open-circuit voltage in kesterite thin film solar cells.

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank Stefano Pisoni for performing the XRD measurements. Financial support from the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNF) in the network of the Indo-Swiss Joint Research Programme (ISJRP) (IZLIZ2_157140/1) and the Horizon2020 program under the project STARCELL

(H2020-NMBP-03-2016-720907) is gratefully acknowledged. The authors would like to thank the whole team of the Laboratory for Thin Films and Photovoltaics.

References

- [1] W. Wang, M.T. Winkler, O. Gunawan, T. Gokmen, T.K. Todorov, Y. Zhu, D.B. Mitzi, Device Characteristics of CZTSSe Thin-Film Solar Cells with 12.6% Efficiency, *Adv. Energy Mater.* 4 (2014) 1301465. doi:10.1002/aenm.201301465.
- [2] L. Grenet, M.A.A. Suzon, F. Emieux, F. Roux, Analysis of Failure Modes in Kesterite Solar Cells, *ACS Appl. Energy Mater.* 1 (2018) 2103–2113. doi:10.1021/acsaem.8b00194.
- [3] J.J. Scragg, T. Kubart, J.T. Wätjen, T. Ericson, M.K. Linnarsson, C. Platzer-Björkman, Effects of Back Contact Instability on $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnS}_4$ Devices and Processes, *Chem. Mater.* 25 (2013) 3162–3171. doi:10.1021/cm4015223.
- [4] T. Feuerer, B. Bissig, T.P. Weiss, R. Carron, E. Avancini, J. Löckinger, S. Buecheler, A.N. Tiwari, Single-graded CIGS with narrow bandgap for tandem solar cells, *Sci. Technol. Adv. Mater.* 19 (2018) 263–270. doi:10.1080/14686996.2018.1444317.
- [5] S. Chen, X.G. Gong, A. Walsh, S.-H. Wei, Electronic structure and stability of quaternary chalcogenide semiconductors derived from cation cross-substitution of II-VI and I-III-VI₂ compounds, *Phys. Rev. B.* 79 (2009) 165211. doi:10.1103/PhysRevB.79.165211.
- [6] C.-I. Lee, C.-D. Kim, Optical properties of undoped and Co^{2+} -doped $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnGeSe}_4$ crystals, *J. Korean Phys. Soc.* 37 (2000) 364–367.
- [7] T. Schnabel, M. Seboui, E. Ahlswede, Band Gap Tuning of $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnGeS}_x\text{Se}_{4-x}$ Absorbers for Thin-Film Solar Cells, *Energies.* 10 (2017) 1813. doi:10.3390/en10111813.
- [8] S. Kim, K.M. Kim, H. Tampo, H. Shibata, K. Matsubara, S. Niki, Ge-incorporated $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnSe}_4$ thin-film solar cells with efficiency greater than 10%, *Sol. Energy Mater. Sol. Cells.* 144 (2016) 488–492. doi:10.1016/j.solmat.2015.09.039.
- [9] K. Woo, Y. Kim, W. Yang, K. Kim, I. Kim, Y. Oh, J.Y. Kim, J. Moon, Band-gap-graded $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSn}(\text{S}_{1-x}\text{Se}_x)_4$ Solar Cells Fabricated by an Ethanol-based, Particulate Precursor Ink Route, *Sci. Rep.* 3 (2013) 3069. doi:10.1038/srep03069.
- [10] K.-J. Yang, D.-H. Son, S.-J. Sung, J.-H. Sim, Y.-I. Kim, S.-N. Park, D.-H. Jeon, J. Kim, D.-K. Hwang, C.-W. Jeon, D. Nam, H. Cheong, J.-K. Kang, D.-H. Kim, A band-gap-graded CZTSSe solar cell with 12.3% efficiency, *J Mater Chem A.* 4 (2016) 10151–10158. doi:10.1039/C6TA01558A.
- [11] D.-K. Hwang, B.-S. Ko, D.-H. Jeon, J.-K. Kang, S.-J. Sung, K.-J. Yang, D. Nam, S. Cho, H. Cheong, D.-H. Kim, Single-step sulfo-selenization method for achieving low open circuit voltage deficit with band gap front-graded $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSn}(\text{S},\text{Se})_4$ thin films, *Sol. Energy Mater. Sol. Cells.* 161 (2017) 162–169. doi:10.1016/j.solmat.2016.11.034.
- [12] S.-H. Wu, K.-T. Huang, H.-J. Chen, C.-F. Shih, $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSn}(\text{S}_x\text{Se}_{1-x})_4$ thin film solar cell with high sulfur content (x approximately 0.4) and low Voc deficit prepared using a postsulfurization process, *Sol. Energy Mater. Sol. Cells.* 175 (2018) 89–95. doi:10.1016/j.solmat.2017.09.036.
- [13] Y.-F. Qi, D.-X. Kou, W.-H. Zhou, Z.-J. Zhou, Q.-W. Tian, Y.-N. Meng, X.-S. Liu, Z.-L. Du, S.-X. Wu, Engineering of interface band bending and defects elimination via a Ag-graded active layer for efficient $(\text{Cu},\text{Ag})_2\text{ZnSn}(\text{S},\text{Se})_4$ solar cells, *Energy Environ. Sci.* 10 (2017) 2401–2410. doi:10.1039/C7EE01405H.

- [14] J. Márquez, H. Stange, C.J. Hages, N. Schaefer, S. Levchenko, S. Giraldo, E. Saucedo, K. Schwarzburg, D. Abou-Ras, A. Redinger, M. Klaus, C. Genzel, T. Unold, R. Mainz, Chemistry and Dynamics of Ge in Kesterite: Toward Band-Gap-Graded Absorbers, *Chem. Mater.* 29 (2017) 9399–9406. doi:10.1021/acs.chemmater.7b03416.
- [15] C. Andres, S.G. Haass, Y.E. Romanyuk, A.N. Tiwari, 9.4% efficient $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnSe}_4$ solar cells from co-sputtered elemental metal precursor and rapid thermal annealing, *Thin Solid Films.* 633 (2017) 141–145. doi:10.1016/j.tsf.2016.09.048.
- [16] M. Neuschitzer, J. Marquez, S. Giraldo, M. Dimitrievska, M. Placidi, I. Forbes, V. Izquierdo-Roca, A. Pérez-Rodríguez, E. Saucedo, V_{oc} Boosting and Grain Growth Enhancing Ge-Doping Strategy for $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnSe}_4$ Photovoltaic Absorbers, *J. Phys. Chem. C.* 120 (2016) 9661–9670. doi:10.1021/acs.jpcc.6b02315.
- [17] S. Stølen, H.B. Johnsen, C.S. Bøe, O.B. Karlsen, T. Grande, Stable and metastable phase equilibria in the GeSe_2 -Se system, *J. Phase Equilibria.* 20 (1999) 17. doi:10.1361/105497199770335901.
- [18] C. Andres, T. Schwarz, S.G. Haass, T.P. Weiss, R. Carron, R. Caballero, R. Figi, C. Schreiner, M. Bürki, A.N. Tiwari, Y.E. Romanyuk, Decoupling of optoelectronic properties from morphological changes in sodium treated kesterite thin film solar cells, *Sol. Energy.* (2018), *In Press*. doi:10.1016/j.solener.2018.03.067.
- [19] S. Giraldo, M. Neuschitzer, M. Placidi, P. Pistor, A. Pérez-Rodríguez, E. Saucedo, $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnSe}_4$ -Based Solar Cells With Efficiency Exceeding 10% by Adding a Superficial Ge Nanolayer: The Interaction Between Ge and Na, *IEEE J. Photovolt.* 6 (2016) 754–759. doi:10.1109/JPHOTOV.2016.2535236.
- [20] S. Niki, M. Contreras, I. Repins, M. Powalla, K. Kushiya, S. Ishizuka, K. Matsubara, CIGS absorbers and processes, *Prog. Photovolt. Res. Appl.* 18 (2010) 453–466. doi:10.1002/pip.969.
- [21] G. Rey, T.P. Weiss, J. Sandler, A. Finger, C. Spindler, F. Werner, M. Melchiorre, M. Hala, M. Guennou, S. Siebentritt, Ordering kesterite improves solar cells: A low temperature post-deposition annealing study, *Sol. Energy Mater. Sol. Cells.* 151 (2016) 131–138. doi:10.1016/j.solmat.2016.02.014.

List of figure captions

Figure 1: Precursor arrangements for the investigation of Ge diffusion during RTA. The first arrangement consists of a uniform Ge distribution and is used to check for preferential diffusion of Ge and for calibration of the SIMS curves. The second arrangement exhibits a 400 nm thick plateau with a low Ge/(Ge+Sn) (GGT) ratio and increases during 100 nm to a high GGT towards the back. In the third arrangement, a stack of two layers with different GGT is used (“Stacked”). The arrangement is also used for a faster annealing procedure (“Fast”) and with thicker low GGT layer (“Thick”).

Fig. 2: (112) Bragg peak for samples with varying Ge content. The shift towards higher angles with increasing Ge content suggests a full incorporation into the kesterite lattice. The shift allows discriminating the ZnSe phase for some of the samples by an additional peak at 27.23°.

Fig. 3: Normalized EQE for samples with varying Ge content. The bandgap derived from the inflection point increases from 1.00 eV to 1.44 eV for GGT=0.00...1.00.

Fig. 4: SIMS depth profile for an absorber fabricated from a uniform precursor. In order to avoid matrix effects, only the region up to the intercept *of the Ge/(Ge+Sn) line with the Mo line* is considered for the analysis.

Fig. 5: SIMS depth profiles for (left) a weakly graded precursor before selenization which exhibits a pronounced linear back grading and (right) an absorber synthesized from a graded precursor after selenization.

Fig. 6: SIMS depth profiles of an absorber synthesized from (left) “stacked”, (*center*) “fast” and (right) “thick” precursor. The difference in bandgap between the front plateau and the maximum of the back grading is around 40 meV for absorbers synthesized from “fast” and “thick” precursor.

Fig. 7: *Left:* Boxplots of open-circuit voltage for the different precursor arrangements. The dashed green lines refer to the relative open-circuit voltage loss which is indicated on the secondary y-axis. *Right:* EQE measurements of cells processed with different precursor arrangements for kesterite absorber.

List of table captions

Table 1: The nominal Ge/(Ge+Sn) (GGT) ratio from sputter rates as compared to the composition of the metallic precursor and the absorber after selenization measured by XRF. The composition can be precisely tuned at the precursor stage and is maintained after RTA.

Table 2: Photovoltaic parameters of solar cells from different precursor arrangements. Median values for 49 cells per sample are given and parameters for the most efficient cell are given in brackets.

Figures

Figure 1: Precursor arrangements for the investigation of Ge diffusion during RTA. The first arrangement consists of a uniform Ge distribution and is used to check for preferential diffusion of Ge and for calibration of the SIMS curves. The second arrangement exhibits a 400 nm thick plateau with a low Ge/(Ge+Sn) (GGT) ratio and increases during 100 nm to a high GGT towards the back. In the third arrangement, a stack of two layers with different GGT is used ("Stacked"). The arrangement is also used for a faster annealing procedure ("Fast") and with thicker low GGT layer ("Thick").

Fig. 2: (112) Bragg peak for samples with varying Ge content. The shift towards higher angles with increasing Ge content suggests a full incorporation into the kesterite lattice. The shift allows discriminating the ZnSe phase for some of the samples by an additional peak at 27.23°.

Fig. 3: Normalized EQE for samples with varying Ge content. The bandgap derived from the inflection point increases from 1.00 eV to 1.44 eV for GGT=0.00...1.00.

Fig. 4: SIMS depth profile for an absorber fabricated from a uniform precursor. In order to avoid matrix effects, only the region up to the intercept of the $Ge/(Ge+Sn)$ line with the Mo line is considered for the analysis.

Fig. 5: SIMS depth profiles for (left) a weakly graded precursor before selenization which exhibits a pronounced linear back grading and (right) an absorber synthesized from a graded precursor after selenization.

Fig. 6: SIMS depth profiles of an absorber synthesized from (left) “stacked”, (center) “fast” and (right) “thick” precursor. The difference in bandgap between the front plateau and the maximum of the back grading is around 40 meV for absorbers synthesized from “fast” and “thick” precursor.

Fig. 7: *Left:* Boxplots of open-circuit voltage for the different precursor arrangements. The dashed green lines refer to the relative open-circuit voltage loss which is indicated on the secondary y-axis. *Right:* EQE measurements of cells processed with different precursor arrangements for kesterite absorber.

Table 1: The nominal Ge/(Ge+Sn) (GGT) ratio from sputter rates as compared to the composition of the metallic precursor and the absorber after selenization measured by XRF. The composition can be precisely tuned at the precursor stage and is maintained after RTA.

Nominal GGT	Precursor Ge/(Ge+Sn)	Absorber Ge/(Ge+Sn)
0.00	0.00	0.00
0.15	0.16	0.16
0.30	0.29	0.29
0.50	0.48	0.47
0.67	0.67	0.67
1.00	1.00	1.00

Table 2: Photovoltaic parameters of solar cells from different precursor arrangements. Median values for 49 cells per sample are given and parameters for the most efficient cell are given in brackets.

	Uniform	Graded	Stacked	Stacked „fast“	Stacked „thick“
V_{oc} / V	0.430 (0.446)	0.444 (0.463)	0.454 (0.455)	0.488 (0.480)	0.433 (0.445)
$J_{sc} / mA\ cm^{-2}$	31.1 (32.3)	30.9 (34.8)	29.6 (30.7)	23.0 (24.9)	30.4 (31.0)
FF / %	46.1 (50.7)	47.5 (50.5)	45.6 (46.5)	45.3 (49.3)	48.9 (54.7)
$\eta / \%$	6.2 (7.3)	6.4 (8.1)	6.1 (6.5)	5.2 (5.9)	6.5 (7.5)